

CHARACTERISTICS OF CONCEPTUALIZATION OF PHRASEOLOGISMS WITH A COLORATIVE COMPONENT IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. The article effectively analyzes the conceptualization of color in English and Karakalpak, establishing a thesis that underscores the cultural and cognitive dimensions of color semantics. By employing comparative methodologies and referencing a broad range of scholarly work, the author sheds light on the intricate relationship between language, culture, and color interpretation, although the incorporation of concrete examples would further strengthen the analysis.

Key words: color, culture, cognitive conceptualization, paradigm, lexeme, semantics, фразеологические единицы

Colors are a means of clearly demonstrating the unity of each nation, and in this process, the goal is to determine the process of conceptualizing color interpretations in people's minds. At the same time, information was discussed and taken into account about the main criteria for studying colors as an object of study, as well as about the processes of their study. In this case, the research methods are a comparative discussion of color interpretations in English and Karakalpak languages based on historical, comparative, ethnocultural, and cognitive phenomena. The absence of similarity in the lexical layer of English and Karakalpak languages, which are heterogeneous languages, is an axiom, and therefore, the existence of a range of modern languages is possible only if there are differences in this aspect of similarity. According to our hypothesis, the semantics of each lexical unit is related to the functional-semantic description of these terms and concepts, that is, it is clarified that the conceptualization of color terms in English and Karakalpak languages is related to prototypes, metaphorical, metonymic, cultural associations, connotation and aspects that differ from the semantic field.

The study of the phenomenon of color in the context of linguocultural and cognitive paradigms is a simple regularity (from foreign scientists: Berlin, Kay 1969; R. Gackendoff 1993, 2002; V. Berlin, R. Kay 1969; N. Rosch, 1973; J. Itten, 1970; Scientists from the CIS: Vorobyov 1997; Makovsky 1996, 1997; Telia 1996; Maslova, 1997; Krasnix 2001, 2002; Stepanov 1997, 1997; from local scientists: Khojanov 2013; Seytkasimov 2016; Khodjalepesova 2021;

Turabayeva 2021; Kadyrbaeva 2023; Orazimbetova 2024 et al.), their research focuses on the study of linguistic systems, the analysis of structural features of language, the conceptual system, the analysis of problems related to the role of language in constructing all its manifestations, and the identification of cognitive mechanisms for understanding reality. Due to the priority of a sensitive and artistic form of studying the world, color has the ability to change a person's physical and psycho-emotional state, which in turn leads to the stabilization of culture and the formation of a necessary part of the conceptual image with the oldest semiotic system. In myths, which are the source of the most basic knowledge, colors are classified, serve as an element of rituals and beliefs, and at the same time are a means of gathering the most necessary information. Therefore, they become not only an objective characteristic of the world for a person, but also a moral and aesthetic category, expressing indicators, norms, and attitudes saturated with expressive evaluation.

Prototypical images and categories are closely related to color expressions, and color has always been of great importance in human culture, it is closely related to the interpretation of existence as the foundation of the philosophical and aesthetic sphere, in which L.V. Knodel expresses the opinion that "a person organizes himself in his whole existence through more color and harmonizes his relationships with the world" [Knodel 2019: 5].

Color as a physical phenomenon was first described by I. Newton, who studied colors as light waves of a certain length. In his scientific work, I.V. Goethe provides information about color: "the sensation and aesthetic action of color." This thesis states that colors have different meanings and emphasize that they have a certain psychological content, therefore their study requires research within the framework of the mechanical method, based on traditional physics [Goethe 2019: 51]. However, when studying colors within the framework of a mechanical phenomenon, only their denotative meanings are taken into account, while connotative semantics is neglected.

In L.V. Knodel's monograph "English Color Idiomatics," he states that "although dictionaries of different languages contain 100 to 150 names of colors, the human eye can distinguish only 100,000 types of colors" [Knodel 2019: 7]. Researchers define the number of color names differently, and at the same time, they believe that different methods of color research are used. It has been established that the number of color expressions on the Internet exceeds 1028, which makes their research difficult, therefore, we decided to focus on their

semantic properties by dividing the first stage of their research mainly into colors based on their simple functional properties.

N. F. Pelevina identified the differences between the results of the distribution of activity reflected in all the simple forms of different languages and scientific knowledge: "For each nation, there is a special psychological reason for classifying reality, particularly the color field, which is knowledge based on the objects and phenomena of the environment around us" [Pelevina 1987: 152]. A similar position is supported by G. Auberg: "We try to understand each other only when there is a need to regulate and classify our emotions." Only in this case can the words black, white, red, yellow, green, blue be sufficient as basic terms for our senses. The combination and variation of these words is enough to express our feelings based on this color, or at least to convey them in a way that is understandable to other people" [Auberg 1980: 180]. We fully agree with the aforementioned opinions of scientists, and in addition, the entire national image of each nation influences the use of language units through emotions. The colors found in nature are divided into achromatic and chromatic colors, which refer to colors based on the division of colors and a metaphorical or metonymic context based on a person's own experience. Chromatic colors generally include white, black, and gray, while all other colors are chromatic.

According to the assumption of successive stages of color development based on senses, in the first stage, a person's color experience was limited to only being divided into white and black, while in the later period, red and yellow colors appeared [Onol 1996: 21]. In literature on linguistics, which has been studied for almost many centuries, it is observed that the names of new colors are widely used, that is, various images were created through color names. Starting in the 16th century, new color terms began to be actively used in literature, especially in poetry, to create vivid poetic images: "The development of color terms is considered related to the aesthetic needs of literature, that is, the enrichment of the color vocabulary is primarily related to the expansion of simple color terms, often used in poetry, through synonyms in poetic verses..." [Barodina, Gak 1979:37]. With the development of artistic style, the range of color terms expands, with the help of various images, feelings are revealed, and the life of the people is reflected:

Sari boyaw – *kewlimdegi kayǵı – muń,*

Qara boyaw – *táǵdirimniń gúńsı.*

Jasil boyaw - *ármanları jashıqtıń,*

Qızıl boyaw - *júregimniń jarası.*

(I.Yusupov "Gilemshi hayal haqqında haqıyqatlıq", - p. 114).

Along with the development of literature, he contributed to the scientific and technical revolution and the expansion of the color palette. With the development of the textile and dyeing industries, color terminology actively enriched, which arose as a result of the creation of artificial dyes of new colors. The development of color terminology was greatly influenced by the influence of French fashion in Europe at the end of the 19th century, as well as the wave of debt associated with the development of trade with the East.

To understand the specific features of the language, it is necessary to analyze texts that preserve the culture of each ethnic group, primarily oral folk art and fiction. When color names are formed on the basis of cultural associations and specific connotations, they are associated with the historical formation of an ethnic group. Therefore, the empirical material for such research was works in the language of comparison - poetic lines, prose, folklore.

The color scheme of any language reflects the appearance of all languages, expressing certain concepts, feelings, and emotions. The significance of a particular color in the culture of different peoples can vary, therefore the embodiment of colors is determined by the expression of a more or less emotional reaction in the language. This is due to the strong association between ethnic groups, determined by their social, historical, and geographical characteristics. Scholar G.K. Kdirbaeva also expresses her opinion on this issue: "Each member of an ethnic group understands each other because they are aware of the entire language of their community in a national form, based on life experience." For example, in the phraseological fund of the Karakalpak language, "kuk tigilsin" is currently used for Karakalpaks in connotations such as "shame," "compression," and representatives of the ethnic group who know its archetypal meaning understand that it is "gargys" [Kdirbaeva 2023:651].

All associative linguistic color expression is an effective means of understanding other cultures [Alimova 2007:77], it is sensitive to any changes in the color "sign" of society [Alimova 2007:77], it expresses the specific features of personifications, which are firmly linked to national-cultural characteristics [Dmitryuk 1983, 1985].

The semantic field is also taken into account when forming color names. That is, the classification of colors with the same quality helps to identify the differences between them. Moreover, the expression of a typical object embedded in color terms is given through "official interpretations": oq - clear sky, cloud, snow, milk; qora - coal, night, darkness; yashil - grass, leaf, spring.

According to R.M. Frumkina, "the method of explaining color images, which includes an indicator directed directly at the object, is a method that provides broad and accurate information" [Frumkina 1982: 145]. One of the most effective ways to form color names is to transfer color as an object to a description, for example: cherry red - red as the color of ripe silk, grass green - green as plentiful hay, sky blue - blue as a clear sky, golden yellow - shiny yellow as gold, coal black - black as coal.

It is a universally accepted fact that it is impossible to accurately translate (give) color names from one language to another, as an equivalent color name in one language may not exist in another language. The English lexical unit "green" in the Karakalpak language means green and blue, but the lexical unit representing the color "green" is more commonly considered "green."

As J. Lyons notes, "different languages have different numbers of basic color names." However, the correct translation of color names is often an unrealistic activity [Lyons 2004:279].

Among color names, it is one of the means of expressing phraseological units and national mentality. Phraseological units with a color component are embodied on the basis of cultural, mythological, symbolic, socio-historical and other factors through the ability to vividly and figuratively reflect the peculiarity of the people's worldview [Zolnikova 2009: 88]. Phraseologisms, as a living, metaphorical, and emotional means of language, "impose on native speakers special attention to a particular situation," phraseological units help to create an aesthetically significant picture of the world [Maslova 2001: 82]. Since national-cultural concepts are most vividly reflected in phraseological units, special attention is paid to the analysis of phraseological units in English and Karakalpak languages with a component of coloration.

The role of color in the formation of all linguistic manifestations is undoubtedly great, as different linguistic principles and cultural communities connect certain associations, certain color preferences, with the same color. Thus, according to N. Serov, "the change of colors in religion, art, and fashion contributes to the understanding of humanity's identity." Therefore, colors have always and everywhere expressed quality, not quantity or form. That is, it is impossible to reflect in a colorless imagination an action that can be reflected, expressed, or measured, including even the quality of our reason" [Serov 2004: 5].

Colors, which are the main concepts of culture, in all languages express great semantic ability and linguocultural signs of national difference in their

names. Color should be considered in four cases: 1) from an anthropological point of view (social color); 2) from an ethnocultural perspective (cultural-historical color); 3) from a psychological perspective (emotional-evaluative color); 4) from the point of view of linguistic sign (systemic-structural color). Considering the color problem from this perspective implies reconstructing the stages of forming the meanings of color lexemes, reflecting these stages in the context of national-cultural and ethnic differences in the language.

The semantic structure of the meaning of a special color sign is multi-layered. At the core of the linguistic and cultural sphere, interest in color in the most essential phenomena and objects of reality for a person is of particular importance. The initial associations and reactions of colors also represent a set of archetypal, and later mythological, symbolic meanings that are constantly renewed at the boundary of the field, determined by the natural physiological aspect to the meanings determined from them. There is an increase in the use of color in individual cases on a national scale due to the deviation from the semantic center. The universality of color meanings in the languages under analysis is due to the correspondence of their deep layers.

Color has a universal classification function, combining various objects and phenomena of reality, human nomination, social and social, religious and moral, emotional and interpersonal relationships in all comparable languages, revealing a clear logical and relatively rigid system.

Thus, it has been proven that the semantics of each lexical unit is mainly related to the functional-semantic classification of concepts, that is, the conceptualization of color names in English and Karakalpak languages is related to prototypes, metaphorical, metonymic, cultural associations, connotation and features of the semantic field.

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